

Rethinking the use of antimicrobials in livestock production systems

Policy Brief n° 7

Improving the use of antimicrobials in the French pig and poultry sectors

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This policy brief contributes to the main goal of the ROADMAP project which is to analyse the practices and decision systems of farmers, veterinarians and other professionals involved in managing the health of farmed animals, and to the specific objective of identifying levers/incentives for a more prudent use of antibiotics in livestock production

The European Union is the world's second largest pork producer and one of the world's largest poultry meat producers. EU is also a major producer of beef and veal with a total herd of around 78 million cattle and a substantial producer of milk and milk products with a total milk production around 155 million tonnes per year.

This document should be of particular relevant for French policy makers and French pig and poultry stakeholders

CONTEXT

Despite the strong decrease in antimicrobial use in the French poultry and pig sectors over the last decade, room for improvement remains. A participatory approach was set up, involving representatives of veterinarians, the pig and poultry industries, technical institutes, the French Ministry of Agriculture, and researchers, to further improve how antimicrobials are used on farms. By successively defining a shared, long-term vision of future antimicrobial use on farms, identifying lock-in mechanisms impeding this future vision from being realized, and articulating practical questions on how to move in the desired direction, the group rapidly reached a consensus.

The results highlight the need for consensual standardized monitoring tools that would allow farmers and veterinarians to jointly monitor the health, welfare, antimicrobial resistance, and antimicrobial use on farms. Other results relate to better communication and training for citizens regarding animal health, animal welfare, and proper antimicrobial use; some benefits but also counterproductive effects of antibiotic-free labels that imperil animal health and welfare.

These results call for a concerted way to produce tools for farmers and veterinarians and the broader involvement of other food sector actors.

RELATED PROJECT PUBLICATIONS

- Ducrot, C.; Guéin, M.-J.; Hemonic, A.; Rousset, N.; Carré, Y.; Facon, C.; le Coz, P.; Marguerie, J.; Petiot, J.-M.; Jarnoux, M.; Leblanc-Maridor, M.; Paul, M.; Molia, S.; Belloc, C. **Towards a Better Use of Antimicrobials on Farms: Insights from a Participatory Approach in the French Pig and Poultry Sectors.** *Antibiotics* 2022, 11, 1370.
- Guenin M-J, Belloc C, Ducrot C, de Romémont A, Peyre M, Molia S. **A participatory approach for building ex ante impact pathways towards a prudent use of antimicrobials in pig and poultry sectors in France.** *PLoS ONE.* 2022, 17(11).
- Belloc, C.; Guéin, M.-J.; Leblanc-Maridor, M.; Hemonic, A.; Rousset, N.; Carré, Y.; Facon, C.; le Coz, P.; Marguerie, J.; Petiot, J.-M.; Jarnoux, M.; Paul, M.; Molia, S.; Ducrot, C. **Réflexion Participative Pour Une Optimisation De l'usage d'antibiotiques Garantissant Santé Et Bien-être Des Porcs Et Volailles.** *INRAE Prod. Anim.* 2023, 35, 391-400.

Consensus in the poultry and pig sectors

In the French pig and poultry context, the different stakeholders from the production sector (interbranch organizations, veterinarians, technical institutes) share a same vision of the future concerning the use of antimicrobials on farm animals, that is a need for better use of antimicrobials, rather than decreased use.

Farm-level monitoring tools are needed

There is a lack of monitoring tools at the farm level to collect and combine data on animal health, animal welfare, antimicrobial use, and antimicrobial resistance.

Such tools would assist in fine-tuning antimicrobial use to the farm context and benchmarking with other farms with similar contexts.

Citizen and consumer perspective

There is a misunderstanding by consumers and citizens regarding the use of antimicrobials, the resistance to antimicrobials and the residues of antimicrobials in food products.

The multiplicity of antibiotic-free claims generates confusion among consumers.

Antibiotic-free labels discourage farmers from treating sick animals to keep the economic valuation of the charter, which can cause health and welfare issues.

There is a good opportunity for the next EcoAntibio French program to draw up an ambitious perspective for improving the use of antimicrobials at the farm level, from 'less antimicrobial use' to 'better antimicrobial use'.

Actions could be better focused and more efficient by targeting farms with a substantial use of antimicrobials.

Funding should be provided to develop and test multicriteria and combined monitoring tools for animal health and welfare, antimicrobial use and antimicrobial resistance at the farm level.

Once validated, these monitoring tools need to be promoted so that their use becomes generalized.

Organise training and communication campaigns on the use of antimicrobials to treat sick animals, on the absence of residues in animal products, on the welfare issues if sick animals are not treated.

Clarify and harmonize antibiotic-free labels including a clear statement on the need of antimicrobial treatment for sick animals.

